

The Amsterdam Protest Dataset: Linking Visual Archives for Future Research

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Abstract

This dataset is based on imagery of protest, collected across three digitized visual archives and made interoperable through the principles of Linked Open Data with the addition of a thematic classification system.

Introduction

Where power relations exist, protests exist. The history of protest dates back millennia, and in addition to protests being highly influential, shaping country politics, labor, norms and values across the globe, they are also highly visual (Mattoni & Teune, 2014; Geise, Panke & Heck, 2021; Rigney & Smits, 2023). In the case of Amsterdam, the Netherlands, visual depictions of protest have been well stored in archives in the form of drawings, photos, posters, and more, with the earliest known depiction of protest in Amsterdam dating back to 1535. These attestations of protests are, however, fragmented across different collections in different archives. They are usually part of an ‘image bank’, but occasionally these are included in regular collections as well. For a researcher it is therefore difficult to collect and make sense of this material as a whole, especially since a thematic entrypoint is often non-existent. This complicates the (re)construction of historical narratives

surrounding protest, while these narratives are crucial for a fair representation of the ways historical protests have shaped the city we know today.

Archives in the Netherlands increasingly publish their materials as open data in an interoperable format (i.e. Linked Open Data, LOD). While this makes it easier to combine and present material in a thematic research collection, a single access point to these diverse collections is still missing. Addressing this fragmentation, we ask: How can digitized visual archives, digitized newspaper archives and geospatial data be combined into an enriched dataset and be used to generate new research possibilities and insights for studying protest across academic disciplines?

Method

Using protests in Amsterdam as our subject, we created a dataset based on imagery offered by three archives: the Amsterdam City Archives (SAA), the North Holland Archives (NHA), and the National Archives (NA).¹ We linked individual images from these collections to

¹ Data can be retrieved from the archive’s open data services (SAA and NA), or via a data dump (NHA, Van Wissen et al. 2025).

Figure 1 - Screenshot of our Amsterdam in Motion application featuring this data.

the specific events they document: the protests themselves. In addition, as no existing thesaurus sufficiently covered this subject, we introduced a classification system on protest type and theme, made available as a separate thesaurus. While Delpher, part of the National Library of The Netherlands (KB), does not yet provide its data in a comparable open manner, we have linked articles to the protests they describe by means of an initial showcase of the possibilities a linked open dataset has to offer. Finally, we geolocated these images if this was not yet done by the archive, linking via Adamlink to the (historical) addresses and buildings they depict. The resulting dataset, available as open data,² makes it possible to search for imagery of a unique protest across archives, to ask new relational questions based on the added classifications, and to visually map protest over time.

² Zeijlemaker, Z., van Wissen, L., & Verheul, I. (2026). *Amsterdam Protest Dataset - Amsterdam Protest Time Machine* (v1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20429147>

Use cases and potential applications

This dataset has potential for both public-facing and research-oriented use. One public-facing use of this dataset is the interactive protest application we developed for the Amsterdam in Motion museum exhibition (see Figures 1 and 2). Furthermore, we hypothesize that such a dataset (following LOD principles) creates numerous opportunities for interdisciplinary research, combining a digital humanities approach with a variety of other academic disciplines and thus allowing the (re)construction of historical narratives on protest (Phillips, 2012). One possibility is a collaboration between digital humanities and social sciences such as human geography. One well-known and currently salient protest theme that also emerges in the dataset is housing, with notable occurrences such as the Nieuwmarkt uprising of 1975 and the squatters' riots of 1980, as well as lesser known events such as the 1931 rent strikes.

Figure 2 - Example detail page for protest information, showing an individual photo and its metadata.

This dataset facilitates spatial and temporal analysis on the whereabouts of protest, revealing how urban public space is used by both citizens and social movements to protest on a variety of housing issues, and how this evolves over time. With such newly (re)visualized insights, researchers have a new entrypoint to investigate the impact of singular housing protests or waves of similar protests on housing policy, public perception and more.

Limitations

However, one must remain aware of the archive's limitations. Many protests were

never depicted, some decades may be over- or underrepresented, and not all imagery is available to us (yet).

Ultimately, this dataset invites researchers to analyze not only the visible history of resistance, but also the lacunae within the digital archives. By enabling researchers across disciplines to ask new questions about protest based on existing data, we aim to facilitate the writing of new narratives on what (historical) protest means for us today.

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